

1 **CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer represents a primed hESC state.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Elucidation of the primed hESC state recalled CNS metastasis genes including the central nuclear factor mediating CNS metastasis, Sox11, a second Sox homeobox factor family member, Sox21, as well as the Zic family of epigenetic imprinting effectors (Zic3, Zic5) whose expression defines metastasis to the CNS in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.

8 Citations

- 9 1. Messmer, T., von Meyenn, F., Savino, A., Santos, F., Mohammed, H., Lun, A.T.L., Marioni, J.C.
10 and Reik, W., 2019. Transcriptional heterogeneity in naive and primed human pluripotent stem cells at
11 single-cell resolution. *Cell reports*, 26(4), pp.815-824.
- 12 2. Sandberg, M., Källström, M. and Muhr, J., 2005. Sox21 promotes the progression of vertebrate
13 neurogenesis. *Nature neuroscience*, 8(8), pp.995-1001.
- 14 3. Bergsland, M., Werme, M., Malewicz, M., Perlmann, T. and Muhr, J., 2006. The establishment of
15 neuronal properties is controlled by Sox4 and Sox11. *Genes & development*, 20(24), pp.3475-3486.
- 16 4. Bylund, M., Andersson, E., Novitch, B.G. and Muhr, J., 2003. Vertebrate neurogenesis is
17 counteracted by Sox1–3 activity. *Nature neuroscience*, 6(11), pp.1162-1168.
- 18 5. Activation of ZIC family genes in CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer. Mamoor, S. 2025.

19 GSE69692
20 SEEK Co-regulation
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28